

Speciation of ternary complexes of calcium(II) and magnesium(II) with L-glutamine and succinic acid in ethylene glycol-water mixtures

S. B. Ronald and G. Nageswara Rao *

Bioinorganic Chemistry Laboratories, School of Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, India

E-mail : gollapalli@yahoo.com Fax : 91-0891-755547

Manuscript received 21 December 2001, revised 11 April 2002, accepted 23 May 2002

A computer-assisted pH-metric investigation has been made on the speciation of Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} complexes of L-glutamine (Gln) and succinic acid (Suc). The titrations are carried out with sodium hydroxide in varying concentrations (0–60%, v/v) of ethylene glycol (EG)-water mixtures at ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm^{-3} and temperature 303 K. Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} form the ternary complexes MLX_2H_2 , ML_2XH_2 , MLX_2H and ML_2XH in EG-water mixtures. The variation of stability constants with dielectric constant is explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

In continuation of our studies on the speciation of complexes of Gln and Suc with Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} in varying composition of EG-water mixtures¹, we report here the speciation of the ternary complexes.

Results and Discussion

A preliminary investigation of the alkalimetric titration data of mixtures containing different mole ratios of L-glutamine and succinic acid inferred that these two ligands do not form any condensed species². Assuming that there is no expansion of the coordination sphere and three bidentate ligands are sufficient to satisfy the coordination number of the metal ion, the total number of primary and secondary ligands together was restricted to a maximum of three in generating the possible ternary species for modeling. The possible primary and secondary ligand forms and the resulting ternary complex species are MLXH , ML_2XH_3 , MLX_2H_3 , ML_2XH_2 , MLX_2H , MLXH , ML_2XH , MLX_2H_2 , MLX , ML_2X , MLX_2 .

The qualitative evidence for the formation of mixed ligand complexes was obtained from the shift of the precipitation point of mixed ligand systems compared to that of the corresponding binary systems¹. In all the systems, the pH of precipitation for the mixed ligand systems was found to be higher than that for any of the binary systems. Further, evidence was obtained by plotting and comparing the theoretical composite curve with those of the experimental one. The formation constants for acidobasic equilibria of both primary and secondary ligands and those for binary metal complexes were fixed in testing various chemical models of ternary complexes using the computer program MINIQUAD75³.

The log K^{H} values of L-glutamine (L) and succinic acid (X) indicate that LH_2 and XH_2 can exist simultaneously in solution. Similarly, LH_2 and XH , and LH and XH forms of ligands can exist simultaneously. But the simultaneous existence of LH (zwitterionic forms of L-glutamine) and XH_2 (undissociated succinic acid) is possible in a very narrow pH range of 2.5–3.0. The best-fit model was chosen as the one with low standard deviation in formation constants (Table 1).

Table 1. Best-fit models of ternary complexes of Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} with L-glutamine and succinic acid in EG-water mixtures

Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm^{-3} , pH range = 3.0–10.5

EG % (v/v)	log β_{mlh} (SD)			$\Delta \log K$		
	1211	1121	1122	1212	1121	1122
Ca^{II} complexes						
0	16.66 (06)	25.32 (12)	16.34 (09)	21.13 (12)	2.86	2.78
10	17.52 (10)	24.90 (15)	16.11 (13)	20.96 (06)	2.28	1.89
20	17.65 (08)	25.00 (06)	15.91 (09)	21.12 (08)	1.75	1.01
30	17.49 (10)	25.11 (06)	15.97 (09)	21.38 (06)	0.63	0.12
40	16.72 (09)	22.26 (11)	15.98 (09)	21.69 (11)	2.17	1.55
50	–	25.40 (12)	15.85 (14)	22.00 (12)	1.08	0.55
60	–	25.38 (08)	16.01 (09)	22.44 (13)	1.07	0.48
Mg^{II} complexes						
0	19.90 (03)	25.91 (12)	17.02 (09)	24.94 (09)	3.49	4.69
10	19.01 (04)	25.11 (05)	16.44 (05)	24.13 (06)	2.45	3.86
20	18.35 (09)	24.80 (06)	16.21 (09)	23.44 (09)	1.83	2.28
30	17.68 (08)	24.62 (15)	16.00 (16)	22.62 (15)	1.31	1.77
40	17.19 (10)	24.63 (12)	16.03 (06)	22.13 (07)	1.35	0.85
50	–	24.97 (08)	16.05 (05)	22.07 (07)	1.03	–0.07
60	–	25.89 (05)	16.13 (04)	22.54 (04)	2.16	1.60

Stability of ternary complexes :

The formation of mononuclear, unprotonated binary and ternary complexes from a mixture of metal ion (M) and primary (L) and secondary (X) ligands can be shown as the equilibria given in eq. 1.

The change in stability of the ternary complexes as compared to their binary analogs was quantified⁹ comparing the difference in stability ($\Delta \log K$) for the two reactions, ML with X and M(aq) with X with those calculated purely on statistical grounds. The statistical values of $\Delta \log K$ for bidentate L and X are -0.4 and -0.6 for octahedral and square-planar complexes, respectively, whereas for distorted octahedral complexes, the values vary between -0.9 and -0.3 .

Whenever the experimental value of $\Delta \log K$ exceeds the statistical value, it can be inferred that the ternary complex is formed as a result of interaction of ML with X or MX with L. The $\Delta \log K$ values calculated from binary and ternary complexes are incorporated in Table 1 for the systems in EG media. They range from -0.07 to 4.69 in EG for Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} systems. The $\Delta \log K$ values could not be calculated for some systems due to the absence of relevant species.

Higher values of $\Delta \log K$ account for the extra stability of the ternary complexes, which might be due to the interactions outside the coordination sphere, like formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands. Also a similar stabilizing effect may likewise be exerted by the electrostatic interaction between non-coordinated, charged groups of the ligands like NH_3^+ of Gln and COO^- of Suc.

Effect of solvent :

The stabilities of ternary complexes have passed through minima with the increasing EG content except for ML_2XH of Ca^{II} -Gln-Suc which passes through maximum. These trends can be explained as follows.

Ethylene glycol is aprotic, protophilic, coordinating solvent. It is a structure-former and it enhances the water structure in EG-water mixtures, and it removes water from coordination sphere of metal ions, making them more reactive towards the ligands. As a result, the stability of the complexes is expected to increase. At the same time, EG is a

coordinating solvent, and competes with the ligands for coordinating the metals. This decreases the stability of the complexes. Hence, whether the stability of ternary complex is increased or decreased, depends upon the relative impact

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagrams for (A) Ca^{II} -Gln-Suc and (B) Mg^{II} -Gln-Suc in 40% (v/v) EG-water mixtures.

of structure-forming nature and coordinating power of EG. The minima indicate that coordinating power dominates initially and then structure-forming capability.

Distribution diagrams :

Calcium and magnesium form the ternary complexes MLX_2H_2 , ML_2XH_2 , MLX_2H and ML_2XH in the pH ranges 3.5-7.0, 3.5-8.0, 5.0-8.0 and 6.0-10.5, respectively (Fig. 1) in EG-water mixtures. Here, L is Gln and X is Suc.

The species MLX_2H_2 can be represented as $M(L)(XH)_2$ or as $M(LH)(XH)X$. Since the $\log K_2$ of Gln (~ 9.0) is higher than that of Suc (~ 6.0), LH exists in the pH range where XH does not exist, but XH does not exist where LH cannot exist. Hence, the complex must be in the form $M(LH)(XH)X$ but not as $M(L)(XH)_2$. The equilibria for the formation of ternary species are given below :

Ronald *et al.* : Speciation of ternary complexes of calcium(II) and magnesium(II) with L-glutamine and succinic *etc.*

MLX₂H₂ :

ML₂XH₂ or M(LH)₂X :

MLX₂H or M(LH)₂X₂ :

ML₂XH or M(LH)(L)(X) :

Experimental

Solutions of L-glutamine, succinic acid, calcium(II) and magnesium(II) chlorides (E. Merck) were prepared in triple-distilled water. Ethylene glycol (E. Merck; 99.5%) was used. The strength of alkali was determined using the Gran plot method⁵.

The titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations (0–60%, v/v) of EG in water maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ with NaCl at 303.0 ± 0.1 K using a Systronic 335 pH meter. The correction factor⁶ was used to convert pH meter dial reading into logarithm of reciprocal of hydrogen ion concentration. Titrations with different ratios of metal to primary (Gln) and secondary (Suc) ligands (M : L : X = 1 : 3 : 5 and 1 : 5 : 3) were carried out with 0.4 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere⁷. Following some heuristics⁸ in the refinement of the stability constants, the best-fit chemical models for each system were arrived at using the computer program MINIQUAD75.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.B.R.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi, for granting a Fellowship under FIP.

References

1. G. N. Rao and S. B. Ronald, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 796.
2. G. N. Rao and S. B. Roland, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 125.
3. P. Gans, A. Sabatini and A. Vacca, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.
4. R. Griesser and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 1238; 1971, **10**, 2229; 1973, **12**, 1198; 1974, **13**, 462.
5. G. Gran, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **206**, 111.
6. M. S. Babu, J. S. Kumar, G. N. Rao, K. V. Ramana and M. S. P. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 567.
7. N. Padmaja, M. S. Babu, G. N. Rao, R. S. Rao and K. V. Ramana, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 2497.
8. G. N. Rao and R. S. Rao, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 1992, **8**, 12.